

CULTURAL COMPETENCE IN BUSINESS ENGLISH TERMINOLOGY

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The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate the growing importance of intercultural competence in teaching and learning Business English in terms of cultural awareness, which aids in communicating successfully – both linguistically and pragmatically– in a foreign language, in this case English, in various business contexts across cultures. Cultural competence refers to a person's ability to interact, work, and form meaningful connections with others from a variety of cultural backgrounds. The ideas, practices, and actions of people from diverse groups might be considered cultural background. Increasing self-awareness, developing social skills and behaviors surrounding diversity, and learning to advocate for others are all part of the process of achieving cultural competency. It extends beyond tolerance, which indicates a willingness to put differences aside. Instead, it entails recognizing and valuing variety in all circumstances via our words and deeds.

At present, the differentiation of various special areas and their terminologies has reached unprecedented limits, which, according to scientists, is the main communication problem, since it often becomes impossible to understand between different layers of population, between non-specialists and specialists, and even between specialists of the same field. But, nevertheless, if someone wants to take part in this progressive process of cognition, he "will constantly have to master new words, concepts and terms."

In this case, it will be necessary not only to replenish the passive vocabulary, to know as many words as possible and, possibly, to understand them, but also to apply this knowledge. There is a danger that the linguistic competence of individuals will be limited due to a lack of mutual understanding in the communication process. Where there is no general understanding in professional speech, there is a danger of manipulation, which begins at the moment when special languages are used deliberately to hide the real state of affairs.

Thus, the primary task is the interaction between the speakers of professional and general literary languages. Closely related to this problem is the problem of penetration of terminological vocabulary in the composition of the common language and all roles in this composition. Before proceeding to a detailed study of these issues, it is necessary to consider the concept of "cultural literacy". In our opinion, more the exact Russian correspondence to this concept will be the term "cultural competence". Cultural literacy refers to the ability to comprehend a group of individuals from a certain culture's traditions, daily activities, and history. It encompasses their language, art, science, beliefs and practices, as well as their perceptions of their surroundings.

In the Romanian and Russian public consciousness, the very concept of "literacy" is usually associated with knowledge of the rules of spelling and punctuation, the ability to write and read. So, when analyzing the concept of "literacy", Sternin notes that in the explanatory dictionaries of the Russian language, you can find the following meanings of the word "literate": spelling (ability to write), reader (ability to read), normative-linguistic (avoid language mistakes), or other area of knowledge). From a pragmatic point of view, communication literacy is of particular importance - a set of communicative knowledge, skills and abilities of a

person, allowing him to communicate effectively in standard communicative situations in written and oral speech. These meanings, reflect the conceptual features that form the content of the concept "literacy" (Popova 2001: 153-155).

Thus, we see that the meaning of "cultural literacy" is not included in the content of the concept of "literacy" in the Romanian and Russian languages. In English, there is a special concept of "cultural literacy". This concept has much in common with the distinguished I.L. Sternin "communicative literacy", as well as with the concept of "intercultural communication".

The concepts of "cultural literacy" and "intercultural communication" include the component "culture", and both imply culturally determined mutual communicative competence of the participants communicative event. It is "cultures ... that determine the cognitive and pragmatic foundations of communicative activity" (Bergelson 2001: 166).

American scientist E.D. Hirsch defines cultural literacy as "the oxygen for social interaction" (Hirsch 1987: 173). That is why, when determining the types of general knowledge that communicants possess, scientists distinguish two sides: knowledge of the actual sign system and knowledge about the structure of the external world (Bergelson 2001: 167).

Language is closely related to extralinguistic reality, it absorbs the culture of the people, its history, it reflects all the changes that are taking place in society. The extra-linguistic knowledge of the communicants is of great importance. In the process of communication, speakers use common knowledge as starting points. Without them, it is impossible to solve pragmatic problems of communication. V.N. Telia calls this type of knowledge "cultural code"(Telia 1996: 219). O.S. Akhmanova defines them as background knowledge, which is "mutual knowledge of the realities of the speaker and listener, which is the basis of linguistic communication" (Akhmanova 1969: 498) Background knowledge is based on the cumulative function of the language, the ability of the language to consolidate the accumulated collective experience directly in its forms, reflect the features environment of functioning, features of material and spiritual culture, history of the people. National and cultural background knowledge is necessary for an adequate perception of the information

transmitted by the communicant

Cultural competence is essential for successful intercultural communication. Y.A. Shekhtman writes: "the ability to correlate the unknown with the known, placing an object in certain connections and relationships with other objects is the main feature of human knowledge and at the same time the main condition for the success of communication"(Shekhtman 2001: 268).

Interaction during communication depends on the balance between the different and the general in the symbolic systems of the communicants. E. D. Hirsch in his work draws the line on which this threshold of cultural competence lies - between the everyday level of knowledge and the level which is known only to a specialist in a particular field (Hirsch1987: 84).

A characteristic feature of the economic term system is its proximity to the common spoken language. Newspapers, radio, television - this is what surrounds a person constantly, and is a powerful source, including information on economic topics. This distinguishes the term system economics and business from many others, for example, from the terminology system of medicine, where most of the terms are delimited from general colloquial speech, and esotericism is extremely developed. This is due to the fact. That although many medical terms or nomenclature units, such as the names of medicines, are known to many people in the street, when such a word is presented, completely different pictures are born in their minds. While the doctor can instantly recall the composition and properties of the medicinal means, the patient only identifies drugs by their action, and this is often mistaken. The esotericism of medical terminology is also due to the inappropriateness of the general availability of the diagnosis for patients.

The general availability and relative semantic transparency of economic terminology, in turn, is explained by the openness of this terminology and the high level of involvement of the majority of citizens in economic processes. The modern development of economic terminology is carried out in the structure of the space of intercultural communication, in the interaction of language, culture and information. Such a feature is inherent not only in the system of terms in the field of economics, but also in all those terminological systems for which connections with the outside world, society, and culture are significant.

One example is the media terminology system, which has also become a rich source of terminological units that have become commonly used (Molchkova 2003) The researcher says that "the term media system is characterized by the penetration of terms into the layer of common vocabulary." So, the word "film", which appeared in 1905. in the sense of motion picture, is now known to every child: until cinematography gained mass fame, the word remained exclusively within the framework of the terminology of cinematography. After the film industry acquired a mass audience, the word "film" became commonly used (Molchkova 2003: 41).

The development of technical progress has led to the fact that the words, those who came into the language to designate certain specific concepts, known only to a narrow circle of specialists, together with these concepts passed into the sphere of common vocabulary. This conclusion, as we seems to be valid not only for terms in the field of media.

S.V. Sakhievich in his work "Overcoming the diversity of translations of English economic terms" also concludes that "economic terminology is very close to the common spoken language" (Sakhnevich 1998: 15). The paper concludes that the process of convergence of economic terminology and common vocabulary continues as economic reforms deepen.

Researchers note that for most modern industrial societies are generally not characterized by a rigid differentiation of language into more or less closed, self-sufficient systems (Maslova 2001: 81). One of the natural consequences of these processes is the fact that the content of a minimum of cultural competence does not remain static. On the contrary, it changes all the time, replenishing with more and more nominative units (mainly from special areas human knowledge), which is associated with the rapid development of science and technology. V.A. Maslova will give such lexical units the name "industrial" vocabulary (Maslova 2001: 81). According to the SV. Grineva, special vocabulary is not only the main part of the national languages of developed countries, but also constitutes the most dynamic part of them (Griniew 2001: 50). G.V. Kolshansky also notes that the thesaurus of communicants, including those containing terminological units, should be considered as part of their cultural and scientific competence (Kolshansky 1984: 25) This "competence" is the basis for communicants to solve the set pragmatic tasks.

Considering terminological units from the field of economics and business in the aspect of their importance for cultural competence, we can talk about two groups of lexical units: the first group is the "core lexicon" (core lexicon, according to the classification of E. D. Hirsch) where, in particular, includes lexical units of a special area of use, designating concepts known to the layman in this field; the second - lexical units, the semantics of which has national and cultural specifics.

Let us consider in more detail the first component of cultural competence. First of all, it is necessary to pay attention to the closeness of the concepts "consubstantial" terms (Grinev 1993: 27). and "core lexicon" (Hirsch 1987: 67).

It seems that the concept of "co-substantial term" defines the lexical content of a given group of words. This term was introduced by CB. Grinev within the framework of considering terminology, where "consubstantial" terms are defined as lexical units, which are found both in everyday and professional speech"(Grinev 1993: 27). S.I. Treskova, considering the use of terminological units in the texts of mass communication, notes the selectivity of their choice, which is determined by the volume of terminological units and their common knowledge (Treskova 1989: 125). Common knowledge, or generally accepted, is, in turn, reflected in dictionaries, where a dictionary entry gives the meanings of word usage in the order that reflects their common acceptance (Fetisov 2000: 43)

This "boundary" layer of vocabulary usually presents the greatest difficulty in separating terminological vocabulary from the vocabulary of the language. The term is definitely different from common vocabulary.

As already indicated, the peculiarities of terms include consistency, the presence of a definition, a tendency to monosemism within their terminological field, a lack of expression, and stylistic neutrality. In particular, consideration of definition (presence definitions), as one of the terminology criteria, involves a comparison of definitions given by scientific (special) dictionaries and definitions given in explanatory dictionaries of the general literary language.

The differences in these definitions can be demonstrated in a few examples. Let's take the word inflation. The Dictionary of Economics defines it as follows: "reduction in value of a currency. Measured often by

percentage increases in the general price level per year. The Longman Dictionary of English Language and Culture gives a completely different definition of inflation - a continuing increase in prices, or the rate at which prices increase less detailed and. more understandable to the layman. The dictionary of "cultural literacy" gives an even more succinct definition: a general increase in prices.

To illustrate more clearly the differences in the given definitions, we will take one more word - "**monopoly**". A special dictionary will give 5 meanings of this word. Here are just a few of them:

1. exclusive control of a commodity or service in a particular market, or a control that makes possible the manipulation of prices.
2. an exclusive privilege to carry on a business, traffic, or service, granted by a government.
3. the exclusive possession or control of something.
4. something that is the subject of such control, as a commodity or service.
5. a company or group that has such control.
6. the market condition that exists when there is only one seller.
7. (*initial capital letter*) a board game in which a player attempts to gain a monopoly of real estate by advancing around the board and purchasing property, acquiring capital by collecting rent from other players whose pieces land on that property.

In the explanatory dictionary, we find two meanings related to the field of economics - if a company or government has a monopoly of a business or political activity, it has complete control of it so that other organizations cannot compete with it; a large company that controls all or most of a business activity.

It can be seen from the examples given that, despite the fact that the definitions of the same words are given, these definitions differ significantly. The explanatory dictionary gives purely external signs of the designated subject: inflation is interpreted as a rise in prices; the definition of monopoly is given through the description, with a specific example. A special dictionary gives clear characteristics: the deep cause of inflation is the depreciation of money; more detailed conditions and factors for the emergence of a monopoly, etc.

Comparing the definition of a term and the general colloquial

interpretation of a word, we see that the difference between a term and a word reflects the difference between a concept and a representation. This difference, according to S.V. Grineva, "is objectively due to the fact that they reflect phenomena of different levels mental activity - scientific thinking and everyday operation of ideas" (Grineva 2001: 32). Although, here it should be noted such a tendency in the development of language and society, as a movement towards a more meaningful and deeper knowledge of concepts and, accordingly, the meanings of words. I.L. Sternin notes that "in connection with the growth of education and culture, knowledge of the meanings of linguistic signs is deepening" (Sternin 1979: 74).

It seems that precisely such words, which are given definitions in both special and general literary dictionaries, represent that boundary layer of vocabulary, which, being terminology on the one hand also belongs to the common layer of vocabulary. Such words are an integral part of "cultural competence" (a component of general knowledge that includes specialized vocabulary). The number of such words with the development of various spheres of human activity, in particular the economy, grows, and thus expands the concept of cultural competence.

The growth in the number of this layer of vocabulary is indicated by the fact that there is now a much wider variety of terms in the media than was selected by Professor Hirsch in his work "Cultural Literacy: What Every American Needs to Know" in 1987. So, in this we do not find terms such as "auditor" and "regulators" in the publication. In the example below, they are used without explication of the meaning. Since the example is taken from a non-specialized edition, we can do the conclusion is that they should be understandable to an unprepared reader in financial and economic matters.

Pressure was mounting this weekend for a root-and-branch review of the role played by auditors in the credit crunch, following the revelation that Lehman Brothers was able to hide \$50bn (£32bn) of debts from regulators despite checks by accountancy firm Ernst & Young (The Observer - 14/03/2010).

The second group of lexical units is specific to each individual culture. In this case, we will talk about the English-speaking culture and about those lexical units related to the sphere of economics that have a

national-cultural coloration. This coloration is most clearly manifested in the personalities. The process of transition of proper names into common nouns is of a pragmatic nature and can be caused, on the one hand, by the extraordinary capacity of newly formed linguistic signs, and, on the other hand, by the orientation towards the presence of the addressee of the amount of cultural knowledge sufficient to decode the message of the addressee. When a proper name becomes a common noun, "it is filled with a new meaning, which now correlates with a typical activity of the named person, with typical products, with any characteristic local conditions, etc." (Superanskaya 1976: 143)

A change in meaning in a proper name can occur by means of metaphorical or metonymic transfer.

Recently, these tropes, along with antonomasia, personification, allusion, etc., have been considered as "central, not marginal and applied in the study of cognitive processes" (Molchanova 2001: 60). The transition to common nouns is potentially characteristic of all well-known names (Superanskaya, 1973). Thanks to the media, the names of many economic figures, businessmen have become the subject of general knowledge, therefore this area has become one of the sources of proper names, which passed into common nouns (Leonovich 1994: 100) To illustrate this point, here is an example - an excerpt from an article published in *The Wall Street Journal*. The article states that many people are currently trying to appropriate themselves the name "Rockefeller" and lists the reasons that prompted them to do so.

Yet it turns out that calling yourself a Rockefeller is pretty easy-and common. There is a big difference, in other words, between being a Rockefeller and being a "Rockefeller." So just because someone is a "Rockefeller" doesn't mean they are a Rockefeller. And just because someone is a Rockefeller, doesn 't mean they're rich (*The Wall Street Journal* - 30/07/2008).

In these examples, we come across the expression "be a Rockefeller", which means "to be rich." The indefinite article used before a proper name indicates the fact of the transition of a proper name to the rank of common nouns. ... A person who is not familiar with the English-speaking culture does not have enough knowledge to understand the meaning of a message containing this kind rethought lexical units.

This name, which became known first in the English language linguistic culture, over time has become a world cultural heritage and can be understood by a bearer of almost any culture if he has a basic educational level. There are, however, concepts for those or for other reasons that have not gone beyond the framework of the English-speaking culture and are a mystery to people from other countries. Let's take another example:

And whether or not non-compete clauses helped Route 128 companies keep their most innovative employees in the decades after World War II, there's no such argument for them in Massachusetts or Washington today — or so the Toronto researchers' analysis would suggest, though Franco and Mitchell don't say so explicitly. Economy Seattle- 19/08/2008

Not knowing what "Route 128" is, it is difficult to understand what is the meaning of this passage. In the dictionary of cultural literacy, we find the following explanation: "used as a synonym for high technology [high-tech]; this term refers to a highway encircling the suburbs of Boston, Massachusetts, which is known for the concentration of electronics and computer firms located along it. "

There is also a cross-reference to the Silicon Valley article. Thus, we see that the definition of "Route 128" speaks not only of the location of corporations, as it may seem to an unprepared reader, but mainly indicates the specialization of enterprises located in this area.

Such examples demonstrate the law of linguistic economy. This law manifests the human ability, most often unconscious and does not require any effort, to project one phenomenon onto another. In one word, a concept is revealed that would otherwise require lengthy comments. These are stable images for understanding of which "some cognitive operations are used to restore or reconstruct those complete structures of knowledge, the abbreviated analogs of which they are" (Molchanova 2001: 63).

As we can see, these examples very clearly illustrate the role of concepts and terms of economics as a component of cultural competence in achieving the goals of intercultural communication. We can conclude that the economic sphere has become a rich source of lexical units that have become an integral part of cultural competence. Together with that

it is important to note that in addition to the actual terminological units, it also includes culturally colored words, such as names own (names of economic figures, names of organizations, etc.).

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